

LEADERSHIP PERFORMANCE OF SCHOOL HEADS: BASIS FOR DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the leadership performance of the school heads in the public elementary schools in Talugtug District, Division of Nueva Ecija through the quantitative-descriptive research design to determine how the school heads are described in terms of their leadership performance based on self-assessment and those of their teachers along instructional leadership, learning environment, human resources management and development, parents' involvement and community partnership and school leadership. This study also sought to find out the significant difference between the assessment of the school heads and their teachers in terms of leadership performance. Based on the findings, a development program for school heads was proposed to enhance their leadership performance. Weighted means, Z-test and Chi-square were utilized to treat the data statistically. This study has come up to the following results: 1. To improve the professionalism of the public elementary school heads and ultimately their leadership performance, the proposed development program should be considered for implementation so that mechanisms can be put in place for their implementation. 2. There should be a continuous evaluation of the leadership qualities of the school heads for an effective implementation of RA No. 9155. 3. Although most of the school heads are academically qualified, they may still continue to pursue higher education to equip them with advanced, more adequate knowledge, skills and competence to be able to perform their tasks inherent to their positions. 4. School authorities concerned may consider sending school heads to seminars and trainings in which they were found to be deficient.

Keywords: *leadership performance, teachers' assessment to their school head, development program*

INTRODUCTION

All governments around the world are concerned with advancing their educational systems and making them more effective and meaningful. Education provides the basis for the development of the skills of human capital designed to accomplish strategic goals. As such, education must be fundamental. Successful schools are the results of competent governance demonstrated by the school heads in collaborative partnerships with relevant stakeholders. Productive schools have school administrators who dedicate a significant amount of time to planning and overseeing instruction, are extremely visible in the school, and remain loyal to the learning environment (Aquino, 2021).

Leadership has been considered as one of the most important factors affecting school success and excellence. Almost all school factors, whether directly or indirectly, depend on it. Leaders are vital at every level of an organization and cultivating leadership skills early is a great way to pave the way for success.

Educational leaders play a pivotal role in affecting the climate, attitude and reputation of their schools. They are the cornerstone on which learning communities' function and grow. With successful school leadership, schools become effective incubators of learning, places where students are not only educated but challenged, nurtured and encouraged (Verbo, et.al., 2023).

School leaders can make a difference in school and student performance if they are granted autonomy to make important decisions. However, autonomy alone does not automatically lead to improvements unless it is well supported. It is important that the core responsibilities of school leaders be clearly defined and delimited. School leadership responsibilities should be defined through an understanding of the practices, most likely to improve teaching and learning.

As the key intermediary between the classrooms, the individual school and the education system, effective school leadership is essential to improve the efficiency and equity of schooling. Within each individual school, leadership can contribute to improving student learning by shaping the conditions and climate in which teaching and learning occur. Beyond the school borders, school leaders can connect and adapt schools to changing external environment. And at the school-systems interface, school leadership provides a bridge between internal school improvement processes and external reform.

Schools at all levels have huge responsibility and accountability for the education of students through the effective leadership practices of school heads. The goal of school leadership is to ensure to the highest degree possible that every child in every school learns to her or his optimum level. This cannot be achieved with the school principals'

effort alone; it needs cultivating good relationships with teachers so that every child's learning and growth is optimized.

There are numerous approaches in leadership and the effectiveness of such approaches is dependent upon the situation. Research showed that leadership behaviors appropriate in one situation were not necessarily appropriate in another. Nevertheless, despite growing evidence that effective leadership behavior depends at least particularly on the leader's situation, some researchers have reached the conclusion that certain management behaviors are in fact more effective than others in a relatively wide variety of circumstances (Estacio, 2022).

Effective school leadership is that authority to lead need not be in the person of the leader but can be dispensed within the school between and among people. There is a growing understanding that leadership is embedded in various organizational contexts within school communities, not centrally vested in a person or an office. The real challenge facing most schools is no longer how to improve but, more importantly, how to sustain improvement. Sustainability will depend upon the school's internal capacity to maintain and support developmental work, and sustaining improvement requires the leadership capability of the many rather than the few.

According to Espiritu (2021), the school heads as leaders set the direction the schools are going. They are basically responsible for the overall operation of the school. The tremendous changes in scope, variety of competencies, and necessary skills of managing the school make their functions more complex, diverse and challenging. These functions of school heads as educational leaders are essential to the areas of management, namely the vision, mission and goals of the institution, curriculum and instruction, financial and budgeting, school plant and facilities, student services, community relations, and the school improvement plan.

School heads have been traditionally viewed as leaders because of the formal authority vested in their position. Early leadership research attempted to identify which personality traits made a person a leader; the value of using different leadership strategies with people at differing levels of willingness and readiness; the leaders' emphasis on tasks versus relationships; and the extent to which subordinates should be utilized in the decision-making process. Majority of these theories were based on the traditional view of a leader in relation to his/her followers. In-order to expand current understandings of leadership beyond the limiting perspective, it is necessary to challenge the very nature and meaning of the constructs used in defining the subject.

The school head must have a clear understanding of his functions, a desire for knowledge of group dynamics, is academically and professionally honest; has a desire and readiness to cut red tape, is understanding, patient and imaginative. An effective educational leader should possess or develop a vision as an educator. His analysis of problems will certainly provide one kind of a clue about the changes that are needed. He should develop clear, attainable goals and dedicate himself to them; he must have the desire to lead people from all walks of life and demonstrate the willingness to respond to

critics after listening with an open mind. As a good and effective instructional leader, he is willing to take risks.

The school heads as leaders set the direction the schools are going. They are basically responsible for the overall operation of the school. The tremendous changes in scope, variety of competencies, and necessary skills of managing the school make their functions more complex, diverse and challenging. These functions of school heads as educational leaders are essential to the areas of management, namely the vision, mission and goals of the institution, curriculum and instruction, financial and budgeting, school plant and facilities, student services, community relations, and the school improvement plan.

Successful school heads' leadership can be developed and expanded over time. Their ability to reflect on their actions, their own perceptions and the perceptions of others are necessary to complete the challenges of one's endeavor to be effective and efficient. What schools need now is not just to put the right person in the position but training them in competencies that will enhance and sustain an environment of efficient and effective leadership.

School heads spend a large portion of their time interacting with others, the majority of which is face-to-face communication. Failure to interact well with others may hamper their careers since people, whether supervisors, colleagues or subordinates, can make or break a school heads' career. The school head is expected to provide the appropriate leadership which will assist each staff member in making a maximum contribution to the school's effort of providing quality and up-to-date education (Oco, 2022).

While the critical functions of a school head have remained unchanged over the years, the school head's essential role has shifted dramatically. They can no longer function simply as building managers tasked with adhering to rules, carrying out regulations and avoiding mistakes. School heads today must be instructional leaders capable of developing a team of teachers who deliver effective instruction to every student (Dellamas, 2022).

A broad and long-standing consensus in leadership theory holds that leaders in all walks of life and all kinds of organizations, both public and private, need to depend on others to accomplish the group's purpose, and they need to encourage the development of leadership across the organization. Schools are no different. School heads who get high marks from teachers for creating a strong climate for instruction in their schools also receive higher marks than other school heads for spurring leadership in the teachers.

The school heads' work and responsibilities are complex, that a full range of leadership knowledge, skills, competencies, and standards are needed. Every school that promotes lifelong learning, raises student achievement, upholds high teaching standards and advocate school improvement must be led by school heads who are skilled in leadership techniques.

In the light of the significant role of today's school heads in meeting the challenges for change in public secondary schools, the researchers decided to conduct a study to assess the leadership performance of the school heads in the public elementary schools in Talugtog District, Division of Nueva Ecija during the school year 2023-2024.

Theoretical Framework

This study was conceived based on the following theories in support of leadership styles of school administrators – Douglas McGregor's Theory X and Theory Y as cited by Mulder (2015), William Ouchi's Theory Z as cited by Barney (2004) and Abraham Maslow's Theory of Motivation as cited by McLeod (2016).

An individual who embraces his Theory X will view people as inherently lazy, unmotivated, shirking responsibility, and disliking work of any kind. Proponents of Theory X believe workers must be coerced, controlled, and threatened with punishment. The frequent management style of Theory X leaders is to use the "carrot-and-stick" approach to management. In other words, Theory X proponents believe it is necessary to develop a system of rewards and punishments to manage workers and induce them to behave in the desirable way. The Leave No Child Behind Act (2002) and the various state accountability laws were derived out of Theory X principles.

An individual with Theory Y orientation will view other people as workers who naturally enjoy their work and who derive deep personal satisfaction from their work. Theory Y leaders understand that workers are self-directed and self-controlled if they are committed to the organization's objectives. Proponents of Theory Y believe even the average worker can learn to accept responsibility and that all workers, not just managers, can make good decisions.

Theory Z as a leadership style that would lead to greater worker and organizational performance and productivity, as well as higher degrees of worker satisfaction and loyalty. Theory Z is a model based upon five interdependent organizational characteristics: (1) commitment to an overall organizational philosophy; (2) emphasis on the long term development of the organization; (3) the showing of broad concern for the welfare of all workers; (4) workers should be trusted to make their special contributions and to advance their ideas for the solution of problems that they face in the workplace; and (5) participative decision-making.

Theory Z ideas may have some potential for addressing two long-term problems in public education. The first is the weakness of the teacher subculture - specifically a lack of a common language among teachers, the failure of teachers to establish adequate supporting relationships with each other, and the stage lessness of teaching as a career, all which O'Hanlon suggested depresses teacher motivation. The second problem that Theory Z may help address is the segmented nature of the school. Although individual teacher entrepreneurship may provide the basis for teachers to enjoy their jobs, this is inconsistent with the development of the student because learning is a long-term multifaceted process and cannot be accomplished with isolated efforts.

In Abraham Maslow's theory of motivation, there are five levels or human needs, which he refers to as a "hierarchy of needs." The first level of human needs according to Maslow is physiological needs, such as food, drink, shelter, sleep, and sex. These needs include the most basic needs of all human beings. They are survival needs. Few teachers and principals have remained at this level as their profession ordinarily provides sufficient income to meet these most basic needs.

Maslow's second level of needs is the need for security and safety. This second level is closely related to the first level. This level speaks to the need for employees to be free from danger, to be free from financial security, and to be free from other dangers that threaten their physical security and safety. Order and structure are desired in a person's life. A teacher who continuously worries about being assaulted by students at the school may be stuck at this level. Or a teacher or principal may be functioning at this level if he or she does not have sufficient income to pay for extraordinary medical expenses, or sufficient income to pay the mortgage or rent and is thus facing foreclosure or eviction.

As a rule, most teachers and principals have met their needs for security and safety. Teaching is not known to be an extraordinary violent profession with significant risks to physical injury or death. The profession of teaching, although not always true in the course of history, now is widely agreed upon to provide sufficient income to provide a middle-class financial existence for teachers and principals. Thus, few teachers and principals' function at this level.

The third highest level of human needs is the social and emotional affiliation needs of people. These needs include such needs as love, friendship, and acceptance by a group (such as the school staff). Many teachers are highly social beings and extroverts who enjoy being with children and adults in the school. Many teachers have their needs met at this level due to the socialization of many school faculties.

The fourth level of Maslow's hierarchy of needs is the need for esteem and appreciation. These needs include the need for self-esteem, self-confidence, recognition by peers, respect, dignity, status, appreciation, and prestige. It is at this level that we see a large drop-off in the number of teachers and principals who are functioning at this level.

The fifth level of Maslow's hierarchy of needs is the need for self-actualization, or what can be termed self-realization. This is the need for maximum achievement of a person's potential, self-expression, creativity, autonomy, self-direction, and psychological growth. This is the highest level for humans to function at. A teacher whose students year after year show more growth than may be expected may be functioning at this level. A principal who took over a "failing" school and turned it around in a few years may be functioning at this level.

Conceptual Framework

Article XIV, Section 1 of the 1987 Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines states that the State shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all.

Pursuant to Section 6.1 and 6.2 of Republic Act No. 9155, otherwise known as “Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001,” there shall be a school head for all public elementary schools and public high schools or a cluster thereof. The establishment of integrated schools from existing public elementary and public high school shall be encouraged, subject to the guidelines that will be issued for the purpose by the Secretary of Education.

The school head, who may be assisted by an assistant school head, shall be both an instructional leader and administrative manager. The school head shall form a team with the teachers/learning facilitators for delivery of quality educational programs, projects and services. A core of non-teaching staff shall handle the school’s administrative, fiscal and auxiliary services.

Consistent with the law, national educational policies, plans and standards, the school heads shall have authority, accountability and responsibility for the following:

1. Setting the mission, vision, goals and objectives of the school.
2. Creating an environment within the school that is conducive to teaching and learning.
3. Implementing, monitoring and assessing the school curriculum and being accountable for higher learning outcomes.
4. Developing the school education program and school improvement plan.
5. Offering educational programs, projects and services which provide equitable opportunities for all learners in the community.
6. Introducing new and innovative modes of instruction to achieve higher learning outcomes.
7. Administering and managing all personal, physical and fiscal resources of the school.
8. Recommending the staffing complement of the school based on its needs.
9. Encouraging and enhancing staff development.
10. Establishing school and community networks and encouraging the active participation of teacher organizations, non-academic personnel of public schools, and parents-teachers-community associations.
11. Accepting donations, gifts, bequests and grants in accordance with existing laws and policy of the Department for the purpose of upgrading teachers/learning facilitators’ competencies, improving and expanding school facilities and providing instructional materials and equipment. Such donations or grants must be reported to the division superintendents; and
12. Performing such other functions as may be assigned by the Secretary, Regional Director and Schools Division Superintendents where they belong.

Management performance of school administrators from the framework of this study, the school administrator should be skilled in the art of working with people particularly his subordinates in order that improved purposive, planning, directing, implementing, coordinating and controlling will lead to a realization of the ideas of democratic living.

In the process of education, the attitude of school administrators toward their work and their leadership behavior strongly influences the quality of their management of planned objectives. The school administrator should exhibit qualities of leadership which tremendously stimulate teachers' interest in infusing teaching competencies for wholesome leadership traits that foster belongingness to the school organization.

The schools, particularly the elementary level which provides basic education, have their assigned tasks and responsibilities which are increasing in number and significance as society becomes complex. These increased tasks and responsibilities of the schools call for increased stature, personnel and professionals in the secondary school administration where destinies of the schools are directed.

School administration requires a degree of specialization. The elementary school administrator must be a professional expert who must assume direct responsibility for the different school activities. He has a significant role in the instructional program such as in requesting or recommending the hiring of efficient teachers, guidance counselors and other school personnel, in improving for their in-service training and professional growth, in evaluating the performance of teachers and other personnel, in providing instructional materials and equipment, in providing for the various kinds of facilities needed in teaching-learning, in guidance and counseling, in health and physical education, in placement of students, in providing for remedial instruction, in curriculum planning and development, in educational research and other educational activities.

The success of the educational program depends on the leadership of the elementary school administrators, the administrative and supervisory activities undertaken and how these activities are carried out. However, it appears that without the teachers' cooperation with the school administrator, educational management might fail. To a teacher, an ideal administrator must be like a father to a son, or a mother to a daughter in all aspects.

The public elementary school administrators are held responsible for the effective organization and supervision of schools. Leadership style is a concept that has been adopted in the past and it has given impetus to a wide range of leadership strategies. To date, it is a statement that covers a deeper meaning for every school administrator.

The Department of Education's Vision, Mission and Values (VMV) statements serve as guiding principles in its unwavering thrust to provide quality education that cultivates passion for the country that is anchored on a set of core values.

The Department of Education (DepEd) vision dreams of Filipinos who passionately love their country and whose values and competencies enable them to realize their full potential and contribute meaningfully to building the nation. As a learner-centered public institution, DepEd continuously improves itself to better serve its stakeholders.

The DepEd mission is to protect and promote the right of every Filipino to quality, equitable, culture-based, and complete basic education where students learn in a child-

friendly, gender-sensitive, safe, and motivating environment; teachers facilitate learning and constantly nurture every learner; administrators and staff, as stewards of the institution, ensure an enabling and supportive environment for effective learning to happen; family, community, and other stakeholders are actively engaged and share responsibility for developing life-long learners.

Figure 1 presents the schematic diagram of the conceptual framework of the study.

Figure 1

Schematic Diagram of the Conceptual Framework of the Study

The concerns of the study include how the school heads are described in terms of their leadership performance based on self-assessment and the teachers under them along instructional leadership, learning environment, human resources management and development, parents' involvement and community partnership, and school leadership and management and operations.

Based on the findings, a development program was proposed to enhance the leadership of the school heads in the public elementary schools in Talugtug District, Division of Nueva Ecija.

Research Questions

This study sought to assess the leadership performance of the school heads in the public elementary schools in Talugtug District, Division of Nueva Ecija during the school year 2023-2024.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following problems:

1. How are the school heads described in terms of their leadership performance based on self-assessment and those of their teachers along the following:
 - 1.1 Instructional leadership
 - 1.2 Learning environment
 - 1.3 Human resources management and development
 - 1.4 Parents' involvement and community partnership; and
 - 1.5 School leadership and management and operations?
2. Is there a significant difference between the assessment of school heads of their leadership performance and those of their teachers' assessment?
3. What development program can be proposed to enhance the leadership of the school heads in Talugtug District, Division of Nueva Ecija?

Null Hypothesis

This study tested the following hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance:

There is no significant difference between the assessment of school heads of their leadership performance and those of their teachers' assessment.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study was conducted in the public elementary schools in Talugtug District, Division of Nueva Ecija during the school year 2022-2023.

The concerns of the study include how the school heads are described in terms of their leadership performance based on self-assessment and those of their teachers along instructional leadership, learning environment, human resources management and development, parents' involvement and community partnership, and school leadership and management and operations. The leadership performance of the school heads was limited to assessment by school heads and their teachers.

Based on the findings, a professional development program was proposed to enhance the leadership of the school heads in Talugtug District, Division of Nueva Ecija.

Significance of Study

Present trends point more to the school heads as the key people in the realization of national educational goals. No doubt, the implication is that school heads must assume other functions and responsibilities that would otherwise belong to higher-ups. This

further implies that they must possess or develop leadership qualities that will match their multifarious duties and functions.

Thus, the findings of this study would be helpful / important to the following:

Department of Education.

The Department may want to look into the status of the public elementary school heads in the field but who are limited by time and distance for observation. It may use the results of the study that can be modified for use in the formulation of policies relative to the managerial approach of school leaders.

School Heads

This study will beef up suggestions and recommendations that would be helpful to school heads in resolving some common problems they encounter as they assume different roles. They will be guided in using the most effective and efficient ways of manning the school system. The results of this study will provide valuable information to school administrators who are faced with the challenges of administering innovations and changes for their schools. It will provide clear insights into understanding their capacity to stay strong and be focused on difficulties, challenging tasks, and responsibilities of being a leader.

Public Elementary School Teachers

The results of the study will lead them to better relationships between them and their school heads. They will be guided by the leadership practices of their respective heads of schools so that they will be able to cope with their managerial implementation in the school. The institution will be more productive knowing that the school leaders and the classroom managers have a good camaraderie.

Learners

The school heads and the teachers can focus and attend better to the effective and systematic teaching-learning process and more objective management of pupils and pupil problems. Being the recipients of the educational system, they will benefit since they will be provided with better education through competent, effective and efficient school leaders who manage the development and effectiveness of the teachers.

Parents

They will be assured that their children are provided with better education. As the threshold of the nation building, they will be able to adopt different strategies and leadership styles of the school administrators.

Community Leaders.

They can better relate and work with the school heads in projects that can benefit the community.

Community

The work plan and scheduled projects and activities can benefit the community along the following aspects: education, culture, socio-economic, and other concerns.

Researcher Himself

This study will be of great assistance to the researcher himself to guide him in future endeavors as a school head. He will be familiar with the different leadership practices of the school heads. This is a way he could gather relevant information as manager of the institution. This will make him a better administrator towards the end of the day. The results of this research may contribute not only to the development of an effective and efficient administration and supervision of learning institutions but also to the improvement of the quality of life in the institution redounding to the benefits of the different stakeholders of the academic community.

Future Researchers

This study can serve as springboard for future similar studies which may be written in a more intensive approach on a wider base and in another locale. Since education is a continuous process, future researchers may find this study useful and relevant to their study to be conducted. Results of this may guide them in developing their field of study.

Definition of Terms

For a better understanding of the study, the following terms are hereby defined conceptually and operationally:

Human Resources Management and Development.

This domain includes the nurturing and supporting of a learning community that recruits teachers and promotes the continuous growth and development of personnel (DepEd Teacher Education Council, 2017).

Instructional Leadership

This domain covers those actions in instructional leadership that school heads take or delegate to others to promote good teaching and high-level learning among pupils/students (DepEd Teacher Education Council, 2017).

Learning Environment

This domain highlights the role of teachers to provide learning environments that are safe, secure, fair, and supportive to promote learner responsibility and achievement (DepEd Teacher Education Council, 2017).

Management of School Operations

This domain covers the critical role school heads play in managing the implementation and monitoring of their school's improvement plan/annual implementation plan to ensure a safe and caring and effective learning environment (DepEd Teacher Education Council, 2017).

Parents' Involvement and Community Partnership

This domain covers parent and other stakeholders' involvement to raise learners' performance (DepEd Teacher Education Council, 2017).

School Leadership

As used in this study, this domain emphasizes that effective school leaders collaboratively create a vision and establish a climate for teachers, non-teaching personnel and learners to reach their highest level of achievement (DepEd Teacher Education Council, 2017). This was based on school heads and their teachers' perceptions measured and described as follows: 5 – Outstanding; 4 – Very Satisfactory; 3 – Satisfactory; 2 – Unsatisfactory; and 1 – Poor.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study sought to assess the leadership performance of the school heads in the public elementary schools in Talugtug District, Division of Nueva Ecija during school year 2023-2024 through quantitative-descriptive research design.

Quantitative-descriptive research design was utilized to assess how the school heads are described in terms of their leadership performance based on self-assessment and those of their teachers along instructional leadership, learning environment, human resources management and development, parents' involvement and community partnership, and school leadership and management and operations.

The study is also correlational since it sought to find out the significant difference between the assessment of school heads of their leadership performance and those of their teachers' assessment.

Based on the findings, a development program for school heads was proposed to enhance the leadership performance of the school heads in Talugtug District, Division of Nueva Ecija.

Sources of Data

The school heads and selected teachers under them in the public elementary schools in Talugtug District who were chosen based on purposive sampling were the respondents of the study. They provided pertinent information needed in the study to answer the sub-problems raised in the study.

Instrumentation and Data Collection

The main data-gathering instrument used in the study was a constructed questionnaire which dealt with how the school heads are described in terms of their leadership performance based on self-assessment and those of their teachers. The leadership performance indicators were based on the Results-Based Performance Management System Manual for Teachers and School Heads in terms of the domains of instructional leadership, learning environment, human resources management and development, parents' involvement and community partnership, and school leadership and management and operations.

The researcher distributed the questionnaire himself for easy retrieval. Data gathered were analyzed and interpreted through the use of appropriate statistical tools.

Tools for Data Analysis

The following tools were used to treat the data statistically:

1. Weighted Mean

This was used to answer sub-problem number 1.

The formula is:

$$WM = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

Where:

WM = Weighted Mean

$\sum fx$ = the sum of the weighted frequency

N = number of respondents

The interpretation of the data gathered made use of the following reference:

Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Outstanding (O)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Satisfactory (VS)

3	2.50-3.49	Satisfactory (S)
2	1.50-2.49	Unsatisfactory (U)
1	1.00-1.49	Poor (P)

2. Z-test for Two-Sample Means

To answer sub-problem 3 which dealt with determining if there is a significant difference between the assessment of the school heads and their teachers in terms of the former's leadership performance, the Z-test for two-sample means was used.

RESULTS

Leadership Performance of School Heads Based on Their Self-Assessment and Those of Their Teachers

This section presents how leadership performance of school heads is described based on their self-assessment and those of their teachers to answer sub-problem number 1. The leadership performance indicators were based on the Results-Based Performance Management System Manual for Teachers and School Heads in terms of the domains of instructional leadership, learning environment, human resources management and development, parents' involvement and community partnership and school leadership and management and operations.

The data are presented in Tables 1A, 1B, 1C, 1D, and 1E.

Instructional Leadership

Education reforms have created an urgent need for strong emphasis on the development of instructional leadership skills. This domain covers the following actions in instructional leadership: assessment for learning, development and implementation, instructional supervision and technical assistance that school heads take or delegate to others to promote good teaching and high-level learning among students.

Table 1A presents the leadership performance of the school heads along instructional leadership as perceived by themselves and their teachers.

TABLE 1A
Leadership Performance of School Heads
In Terms of Instructional Leadership

Leadership Indicators	School Heads		Teachers	
	WM	DE	WM	DE
• Manages the processes and procedures in monitoring students' achievement	3.98	VS	3.74	VS
• Assists in implementing an existing, coherent and responsive school-wide curriculum	3.52	VS	3.68	VS
• Manages curriculum innovation and enrichment with the use of technology	3.48	S	3.44	S
• Prepares and implements an instructional supervisory plan	3.92	VS	3.74	VS
Average WM	3.72	VS	3.65	VS
Legend: WM = Weighted Mean				
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)		
5	4.50-5.00	Outstanding (O)		
4	3.50-4.49	Very Satisfactory (VS)		
3	2.50-3.49	Satisfactory (S)		
2	1.50-2.49	Unsatisfactory (U)		
1	1.00-1.49	Poor (P)		

As presented in Table 1A, the school heads and their teachers rated the former' as "very satisfactory" in leadership performance along instructional leadership as evidenced by the average weighted mean of 3.72 from the school heads and 3.65 from the teachers.

As reported by the school heads, they have "very satisfactory" rating in managing the processes and procedures in monitoring students' achievement as indicated by the weighted mean of 3.98. They also believed that they are "very satisfactory" in assisting in the implementation of an existing, coherent and responsive school-wide curriculum indicated by a 3.52 weighted mean and in the preparation and implementation of an instructional supervisory plan with weighted mean of 3.92. These are supported by their teachers as shown in the weighted means of 3.74, 3.68 and 3.74, respectively. However, both respondents indicated "satisfactory" rating in the management of curriculum innovation and enrichment with the use of technology as indicated by the weighted mean of 3.48 from the school heads and 3.44 from their teachers.

All these data mean that the school heads are very much involved in assessment for learning, developing programs and/or adapting existing programs, implementing programs for instructional improvement, and instructional supervision.

These imply that school heads as instructional leaders play important roles in facilitating, improving and promoting the academic progress of students. However, more focus should be given on curriculum innovation and enrichment with the use of technology because this is the demand of times with the implementation of K to 12 and DepEd mandate and a learner-centered institution which continuously improves itself to better serve the clientele.

Learning Environment

Learning environment consists of learner safety and security, fair learning environment, management of classroom structure and activities, support for learner participation, promotion of purposive learning, and management of learner behavior.

Table 1B presents the leadership performance of the school heads along learning environment as perceived by themselves and their teachers.

TABLE 1B
Leadership Performance of School Heads
In Terms of Learning Environment

Leadership Indicators	School Heads		Teachers	
	WM	DE	WM	DE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrates knowledge of policies, guidelines and procedures that provide safe and secure learning environments. 	3.62	VS	3.74	VS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrates understanding of learning environments that promote fairness, respect and care to encourage learning. 	4.12	VS	3.68	VS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrates knowledge of an aging classroom structure that engages learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within the available physical learning environments. 	3.88	VS	3.44	S
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrates understanding of supportive learning environments that nurture and inspire learner participation. 	3.42	S	3.74	VS

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrates knowledge of learning environments that motivate learners to work productively by assuming responsibility for their own learning. 	3.55	VS	3.60	VS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrates knowledge of positive and non-violent discipline in the management of learner behavior. 	3.11	S	3.20	S
Average WM	3.62	VS	3.57	VS
Legend: WM = Weighted Mean				
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)		
5	4.50-5.00	Outstanding (O)		
4	3.50-4.49	Very Satisfactory (VS)		
3	2.50-3.49	Satisfactory (S)		
2	1.50-2.49	Unsatisfactory (U)		
1	1.00-1.49	Poor (P)		

As presented in Table 1B, the school heads and their teachers rated the former as “very satisfactory” in leadership performance along learning environment as evidenced by the average weighted mean of 3.72 from the school heads and 3.65 from the teachers.

As reported by the school heads, they have “very satisfactory” rating in demonstrating knowledge of policies, guidelines and procedures that provide safe and secure learning environments as indicated by the weighted mean of 3.62. They also believed that they are “very satisfactory” in demonstrating understanding of learning environments that promote fairness, respect and care to encourage learning indicated by a 4.12 weighted mean and in demonstrating knowledge of learning environments that motivate learners to work productively by assuming responsibility for their own learning with weighted mean of 3.55. These are supported by their teachers as shown in the weighted means of 3.74, 3.68 and 3.60, respectively. However, both respondents indicated “satisfactory” rating in demonstrating knowledge of positive and non-violent discipline in the management of learner behavior as indicated by the weighted mean of 3.11 from the school heads and 3.20 from their teachers.

All these data mean that the school heads are very much involved in assessment for learning, developing programs and/or adapting existing programs, implementing programs for instructional improvement, and instructional supervision.

These imply therefore that the school heads assured students of a safe and secure positive learning environment where a classroom community and culture remain necessary aspects in fostering a safe learning environment.

Human Resources Management and Development

Effective school leaders develop the skills and talents of those around them. This domain includes the nurturing and supporting of a learning community that recruits teachers and promotes the continuous growth and development of personnel.

Table 1C presents the leadership performance of the school heads along human resources management and development as perceived by themselves and their teachers.

TABLE 1C
Leadership Performance of School Heads
In Terms of Human Resources Management
and Development

Leadership Indicators	School Heads		Teachers	
	WM	DE	WM	DE
• Builds a community of learners among teachers	4.00	VS	4.21	VS
• Utilizes the basic qualification standards and adheres to pertinent policies in recruiting and hiring teachers/staff	3.88	VS	3.52	VS
• Manages performance of teachers and staff	3.60	VS	3.60	VS
• Recommends and coordinates services for the holistic development of school personnel and learners	3.60	VS	3.53	VS
• Organizes and conducts school-based in-service trainings	3.68	VS	3.60	VS
Average WM	3.75	VS	3.69	VS
Legend: WM = Weighted Mean				
Point Values	Statistical Limits		Descriptive Equivalent (DE)	
5	4.50-5.00		Outstanding (O)	
4	3.50-4.49		Very Satisfactory (VS)	
3	2.50-3.49		Satisfactory (S)	
2	1.50-2.49		Unsatisfactory (U)	
1	1.00-1.49		Poor (P)	

From Table 1C, the school heads and their teachers indicated “very satisfactory” leadership performance along human resource management as evidenced by the average weighted mean of 3.83 from the school heads and 3.78 from their teachers.

Building a community of learners among teachers, utilizing the basic qualification standards and adhering to pertinent policies in recruiting and hiring teachers / staff, and managing performance of teachers and staff were given weighted means of 4.00, 3.88

and 3.60, respectively by the school heads, while those of the teachers were weighted means of 4.21, 3.52 and 3.60, respectively.

These results mean that the school heads recognize individual talents and assign responsibility for specific tasks and appraise the staff based on competency standards. This implies that the school heads are competent in creating a professional learning community, recruitment and hiring, and managing performance of teachers and staff.

Parents' Involvement and Community Partnership

Effective school heads engage in shared decision making with the community in achieving universal participation, completion and functional literacy. This domain covers parent and other stakeholders' involvement to raise learners' performance.

The leadership performance of the school heads along partnership with parents and the community as perceived by themselves and their teachers is presented in Table 1D.

TABLE 1D
Leadership Performance of School Heads
In Terms of Parents' Involvement and Community Partnership

Leadership Indicators	School Heads		Teachers	
	WM	DE	WM	DE
• Organizes programs that involve parents and other school stakeholders to promote learning	3.40	S	2.75	S
• Participates actively in community affairs	3.62	VS	2.81	S
• Establishes linkages with stakeholders	3.75	VS	3.33	S
• Designs programs/projects with stakeholders to address school needs	3.76	VS	3.41	S
• Formulates school policies with stakeholders	3.53	VS	3.40	S
Average WM	3.61	VS	3.14	S
Legend: WM = Weighted Mean				
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)		
5	4.50-5.00	Outstanding (O)		
4	3.50-4.49	Very Satisfactory (VS)		
3	2.50-3.49	Satisfactory (S)		
2	1.50-2.49	Fair (F)		
1	1.00-1.49	Poor (P)		

As presented in Table 1D, the school heads believed they are “satisfactory” in organizing programs that involve parents and other school stakeholders to promote learning as indicated by the weighted mean of 3.40. The teachers had similar perceptions as shown by the weighted mean of 2.75. In participating actively in community affairs, the school heads assessed themselves “very satisfactory” with a weighted mean of 3.62; however, their teachers assessed them “satisfactory” with a weighted mean of 2.81. The average weighted mean was 3.51 described as “very satisfactory” from the school heads and 2.78 described as “satisfactory” from their teachers. These results show the responsibility for promoting positive image of the school thereby establishing sustainable linkages with other sectors.

Partnership with parents and the community involves school improvement, strengthened families, building community support, and increased student achievement and success. However, the partnership had only “satisfactory” rating as perceived by the teachers which implies that the school heads still need to increase their involvement in community activities.

School Leadership and Management and Operations

Effective leadership is the core of every successful school. This domain emphasizes that effective school leaders collaboratively create a vision and establish a climate for teachers, non-teaching personnel and learners to reach their highest level of achievement. The domain of school management and operations covers the critical role school heads play in managing the implementation and monitoring of their school’s improvement plan/annual implementation plan.

Table 1E presents the leadership qualities of the school heads as perceived by themselves and their teachers along with school leadership.

TABLE 1E
Leadership Performance of School Heads
In Terms of School Leadership and
Management and Operations

Leadership Qualities	School Heads		Teachers	
	WM	DE	WM	DE
• Develops and communicates Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives (VMGO)	4.00	VS	4.21	VS
• Communicates effectively SIP/AIP to internal and external stakeholders	3.28	S	3.44	S
• Assists teachers and students to understand problems and identify possible solutions	3.78	VS	3.52	VS
	3.60	VS	3.52	VS

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitors and evaluates accomplishments of different committees/teams 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborate with concerned staff on the planning and implementation of programs and projects 	3.65	VS	2.75	S
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advocates and executes plans for changes including culture change in the workplace 	3.40	S	3.02	S
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institutionalizes best practices in managing and monitoring school operations thereby creating a safe, secure and clean learning environment 	4.00	VS	4.21	VS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manages school resources in accordance with DepEd policies and accounting and auditing rules and regulations and other pertinent guidelines 	3.88	VS	3.52	VS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use information technology to facilitate the operationalization of the school management systems 	3.67	VS	3.60	VS
Average WM	3.70	VS	3.53	VS
Legend: WM = Weighted Mean				
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)		
5	4.50-5.00	Outstanding (O)		
4	3.50-4.49	Very Satisfactory (VS)		
3	2.50-3.49	Satisfactory (S)		
2	1.50-2.49	Unsatisfactory (U)		
1	1.00-1.49	Poor (P)		

As presented in Table 1E, the leadership performance of the school heads along school leadership and management and operations is “very satisfactory” as manifested by the overall weighted mean of 3.70 from the school heads; their teachers perceived their performance to be also “satisfactory” by the overall weighted mean of 3.53.

Specifically, the school heads and their teachers have similar perceptions of “very satisfactory” in developing and communicating vision, mission, goals, and objectives (VMGO) with weighted means of 4.00 and 4.21, respectively. This is again evident in problem-solving with weighted mean of 3.78 from the school heads and 3.52 from their teachers and in monitoring and evaluating accomplishments for weighted means of 3.60 and 3.52, respectively. The school heads and their teachers have the same perceptions again in communicating SIP/AIP with weighted means of 3.28 and 3.44, respectively for

“satisfactory” descriptive equivalent and in advocating and executing plans for changes with weighted means of 3.40 and 3.02, respectively.

Their perceptions differ however, in collaborating with concerned staff on planning and implementation of programs and projects with 3.65 weighted mean from the school heads for “very satisfactory” and 2.75 as “satisfactory” from their teachers.

Generally, leadership performance along with school leadership involves developing and communicating vision, mission, goals, and objectives (VMGO), data-based strategic planning, problem-solving, building high performance teams, coordinating with others, and leading and managing change.

The school heads believed they institutionalize best practices in managing and monitoring school operations thereby creating a safe, secure and clean learning environment (WM=4.00); they believed they manage school resources in accordance with DepEd policies and accounting and auditing rules and regulations and other pertinent guidelines (Mean=3.88); and they believed they use information technology to facilitate the operationalization of the school management services (WM=3.67). All these resulted with “very satisfactory” performance.

The teachers supported their school heads through weighted means of 4.21, 3.52 and 3.60, respectively for a descriptive equivalent of “very satisfactory.” They are aware that the school heads are responsible for the generation, mobilization and are accountable for the utilization of funds and other resources. They also use ICT in the management of their daily operations.

These results imply that the school heads follow the leadership framework of a transformational leadership which is owning, co-owning and co-creating. They use data base and analysis of best practices in education, society and country to be responsive and proactive in changing schools to prepare students for the future. These results also imply that school heads have the knowledge, skills and competence in managing school operations, fiscal management and use of technology in the management of operations.

As presented in the Summary Table, all performance indicators were “very satisfactory” except for one which was “satisfactory.” The “very satisfactory” descriptive equivalent ranged from 3.53 to 3.75. The overall weighted means were 3.68 and 3.52 from the school heads and the teachers, respectively, both for descriptive equivalent of “very satisfactory.” This indicates that generally, the performance of the school heads exceeded expectations. All goals, objectives and targets were achieved above the established standards.

SUMMARY TABLE

Leadership Indicators	School Heads		Teachers	
	WM	DE	WM	DE
• Instructional leadership	3.72	VS	3.65	VS
• Learning environment	3.62	VS	3.57	VS
• Human resources management and development	3.75	VS	3.69	VS
• Parents' involvement and community partnership	3.61	VS	3.14	S
• School leadership and management and operations	3.70	VS	3.53	VS
OVERALL, WM	3.68	VS	3.52	VS

Difference Between the Assessment of the School Heads and their Teachers

This section presents the difference between the assessment of the school heads and their teachers in terms of the former's leadership performance to answer sub-problem number 2. The results are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2
Difference Between the Assessment of School Heads and Teachers on School Heads' Leadership Performance

	Mean	Variance	Mean Difference	p-value
School Heads	3.68	0.06	0.16	0.0495*
Teachers	3.52	0.14		

**not significant difference at .05 level of significance*

As presented in Table 2, the mean for the school heads was 3.68 while that of the teachers was 3.52 for a mean difference of 0.16. With p-value of 0.0495 at 0.05 level of significance, there is no significant difference in the perceptions of the school heads and the teachers on the former's leadership performance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. The results mean that the school heads rated themselves comparably the same as their teachers' rating on their leadership performance.

Proposed Development Program to Enhance the Leadership of the School Heads

This section presents the proposed development program to enhance the leadership of the school heads in the public elementary schools in Talugtug District, Division of Nueva Ecija to answer sub-problem number 3.

The proposed development program focuses on school leadership, internal stakeholders, external stakeholders, school improvement process, school-based resources, and school performance accountability.

DISCUSSION

This study assessed the leadership performance of the school heads in the public elementary schools in Talugtug District, Division of Nueva Ecija during school year 2023-2024 through the quantitative-descriptive research design.

The quantitative-descriptive research design was utilized in the determination of how the school heads are described in terms of their leadership performance based on self-assessment and those of their teachers along instructional leadership, learning environment, human resources management and development, parents' involvement and community partnership and school leadership and management and operations.

The study is also correlational since it sought to find out the significant difference between the assessment of the school heads and their teachers in terms of leadership performance.

Based on the findings, a development program for school heads was proposed to enhance the leadership performance of the school heads in the public elementary schools in Talugtug District, Division of Nueva Ecija.

The school heads and teachers under them in the public elementary schools in Talugtug District were the respondents of the study. They provided pertinent information needed in the study to answer the sub-problems raised in the study.

Weighted mean and Z-test were utilized to treat the data statistically.

Summary of Findings

1.0 How the School Heads are Described in Terms of their Leadership Performance

- 1.1 Along instructional leadership, the school heads rated themselves "very satisfactory" with average weighted mean of 3.72 while the teachers rated them "very satisfactory" also with weighted mean of 3.65.

- 1.2 Along learning environment, the school heads' and the teachers' ratings were both "very satisfactory" with average weighted means of 3.62 and 3.57, respectively.
- 1.3 Along human resources management and development, both groups of respondents rated the school heads as "very satisfactory" with average weighted means of 3.75 and 3.69, respectively.
- 1.4 Along parents' involvement and community partnership, the school heads rated themselves as "very satisfactory" with average weighted mean of 3.61; however, the teachers rated them "satisfactory" with a weighted mean of 3.14.
- 1.5 Along school leadership and management and operations, the school heads rated themselves "very satisfactory" with average weighted mean of 3.70; the teachers rated them "very satisfactory" also with average weighted mean of 3.53.
- 1.6 The overall means were 3.68 and 3.52 from the school heads and the teachers, respectively for descriptive equivalent of "very satisfactory" for both groups of respondents.

2.0 Difference Between the Assessment of the School Heads and their Teachers

There is no significant difference in the perceptions of the school heads and the teachers on the former's leadership performance; thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. The school heads rated themselves comparable the same as their teachers' rating on their leadership performance.

3.0 Proposed Development Program

A development program was proposed to enhance the leadership of the school heads in the public elementary schools in Talugtug District, Division of Nueva Ecija.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Generally, the school heads have very satisfactory leadership performance which means their performance exceeded expectations and all goals, objectives and target were achieved above the established standards.
2. There is no significant difference between the assessment of the school heads and their teachers in terms of leadership performance. The school heads rated themselves comparably the same as their teachers' rating on their leadership performance.
3. The proposed development program focused on the needs of the school heads for improving their use of appropriate leadership styles and improving their supervisory skills.

Recommendations

On the basis on the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations were offered:

1. To improve the professionalism of the public elementary school heads and ultimately their leadership performance, the proposed development program should be considered for implementation so that mechanisms can be put in place for their implementation.
2. There should be a continuous evaluation of the leadership qualities of the school heads for an effective implementation of RA No. 9155.
3. Although most of the school heads are academically qualified, they may still continue to pursue higher studies in the Graduate Studies to equip them with advanced and more adequate knowledge, skills and competence to be able to perform their tasks inherent to their positions.
4. School authorities concerned may consider sending school heads to seminars and trainings in international levels in which they were found to be deficient.
5. Other researchers may conduct a similar study on a wider scope to validate the findings of the study.

PROPOSED DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

Rationale

Leadership can play a key role in informing learning outcomes of learners by setting strategic direction and goal, influencing teachers' behaviors and keeping teachers and learners focused on teaching.

Areas of Concern	Objectives	Strategies/Activities	Expected Outcome
School Leadership	To be aware of his/her basic roles and responsibilities in school improvement To initiate organization of stakeholders and document roles and responsibilities of each organized internal / external stakeholders group	Attendance in induction and/or orientation on basic leadership and management roles of the school head Documentation – School Annual Improvement Plan <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation of Teachers Performance • Meetings with school stakeholders on school targets reflecting 	Being accountable to school stakeholders

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To initiate the installation of the required SBM mechanics / systems 	<p>performance evaluation results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staff development program based on National Competency-Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS) • Training and orientation on SBM provided by the school head to internal and external stakeholders • Meetings with student organizations, parent organizations, teacher organizations, LGUs, and local organizations • Implementation of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Management Information Systems (MIS) - School Improvement Planning (SIP) system - Budget and Resource Management (BRM) system - School staffing system - Teachers' welfare system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective work relationship with organized stakeholders to champion SBM for continuous school improvement • Institutionalized SBM system through shared leadership
Internal Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To be aware of the pupils/students' teachers, parent's rights and responsibilities as primary stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in the development and implementation of the SIP/AIP • Meetings, feedback and suggestions for school improvement • Consultations concerning student performance • Status reports on projects/programs and their contributions to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active co-leaders of the school and assume shared responsibility • Continuing professional development

		<p>the improvement of learning outcomes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training on curriculum context and pedagogy 	
External stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To support/implement SBM • To expand school wide support for implementation of SIP priority programs and pupils 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consultation sessions with other stakeholders regarding feedback on performance • Participation of external stakeholders in SIP implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared responsibility and accountability towards students learning outcomes
School Improvement Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To conduct assessment of SBM practices using assessment tools • To organize School Governing Council 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of SBM assessment results • Records of technical assistance and actions taken in improving SBM • List of projects and activities identified by SGC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous school improvement process
School-Based Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attainment of school targets and desired learning outcomes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Records of resources/funds received from LGUs and other sources • Documentation of best practices on fund management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full fiscal authority / Autonomy
School Performance Accountability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To have mechanisms for transparency and accountability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of SIP/AIP • Tracking of student performance • Tracking of teacher's performance • SGC operations • Fund management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Functional monitoring and evaluation system

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this research, ethical considerations were prioritized to ensure the protection and respect of all participants involved. Informed consent was obtained from the respondents, with a clear explanation of the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the study by using codes instead of names and securely storing all data. Participation

was entirely voluntary, with the option to withdraw at any time without penalty. No conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research. Moreover, the study adhered to institutional and educational ethical guidelines.

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